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THE IMPORTANCE OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS IN STRENGTHENING BRIDGE ELEMENTS

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Abstract. In addition to the development in the rapidly developing era of current technology and technology, various shortcomings also arise. An increase in the number of inhabitants and cars in the use of bridge structures, an increase in the volume of cargo as a result of industrial development, is causing an increase in the need for cargo and passenger transport every year. This results in various types of defects and damage to the bridge elements. The solution to this issue was usually the use of reinforced concrete materials, which in turn would lead to the aggravation of the bridge structure as well as the high cost of Labor. This article addresses the issue of solving the aforementioned problem using lightweight and robust composite materials.

Key words: Bridge elements, supports, intermediate devices, defects and damage, composite materials, ugleplasts.

INTRODUCTION

To date, intermediate devices have defects and damage due to long-term and heavy working conditions, directly or indirectly affecting their load-bearing capacity. Special attention should be given to the intermediate devices of the conductors, many of such structures are damaged by the impact of large-scale vehicles, since the size of the bridge is not enough for its safe passage. The application of composite materials based on carbon fiber the quality of the reinforcement material is a promising technology, the effectiveness of which has been proven by many experimentally [1-4].

During the period of operation and over time, bridges, like any other construction structure, deform and wear out. Under the influence of weather conditions, due to high humidity and due to overloading on the surfaces of bridge supports, cracks may appear, destruction of stone work, surfaces may be in weather conditions. Especially often areas where the water level changes or ICE

drops are observed are doomed. The bridge supports are often damaged due to increased load on the bridge. Traffic on bridges is constantly growing, so even bridges built 5 or 10 years ago cannot be safe [4,5].

Bridges and overpasses are subject to several types of loads:

- * own weight,
- * non-stop car traffic,
- * pedestrian movement,
- * grunt shift,
- * seismic activity in specific areas.

In some cases, the reinforcement of the bridge supports should not be delayed.

* If the structures collapsed during Operation. The supports, beams and other load-bearing structures of the bridges constantly receive large loads. During Operation, cracks and cracks will inevitably appear, which will increase in size over time. If measures are not taken to strengthen load-bearing structures in time, the safety of the object is threatened.

* Increased load on bridge supports requires constant attention and keeping the load-

bearing elements of the bridge in working condition. In particular, it is necessary to carefully monitor the damage and breakdowns of the submerged bridge supports. It is usually the most difficult to observe such parts of the supports [6].

Signs of breakage of bridge supports

Dangerous signs of violation of bridge supports are the stratification of the concrete surface, the presence of irregularities and irregularities, the appearance of small cracks. Such defects are caused by the penetration of concrete and changes in temperature.

Strengthening of bridge structures is usually carried out on the basis of the nature of the defect and the reasons for their occurrence. Small cracks formed by concrete penetration or temperature changes usually do not affect the load-bearing capacity of bridges, but cracks or holes caused by mechanical damage must be closed without delay, as they can affect the load-bearing capacity of the entire bridge structure. Visual inspection of bridge supports and striking surfaces allow the most defects to be detected [6-8].

METHOD OF RESEARCH

There are several traditional ways to strengthen bridges:

- * supports are reinforced using special steel "shirts",
- * another thick layer of concrete is applied over the existing layer of concrete,
- * several more supports and beams are installed [6].

Reinforcement of supports

When reconstructing bridges using reinforced concrete, pile supports are often insufficient for the support of bridge intermediate devices and will need to be expanded. It is considered much cheaper and more convenient to expand the surface of the

supports with the concealer of cracks than to build it new.

Horizontal straps from one or more carcasses with a height of 1-1.5 m and a thickness of 25-40 CM are used on intermediate supports.

The number of straps depends on the position of the base. Horizontal slits are fastened with one belt, while vertical and oblique slits are fastened with two or three or more belts depending on the height of the base (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Scheme of strengthening the intermediate support with a reinforced concrete belt

When installing the belt along the base height, the upper belt should be below the cornice stone, and the lower belt should be above the saddle (the middle line of the water). The distance between the axes of the belts along the height of the base should not be less than the thickness of the base on the facade. Belts are reinforced like shells, a set of 25 mm diameter sterjen fittings is used, metal anchors with a diameter of 18-25 mm and a length of 50-75 CM are used for machining [3].

When strengthening the supports using ugleplasts, a ugleplastic fabric is installed vertically in the base structure at angles of Radius up to 20 mm. Ribbons with a one-or two-way Braid are used for mounting horizontally (in a circle, with an equal interval

along the entire base). In addition, tape, slats for laying around the base head and clamps for the inclined part of the base head are used.

The direction of operation of carbon fiber should be selected the same as the direction of deformation impact on the supports. The number of layers is calculated based on the desired reinforcement indicators [6-8].

Strengthening intermediate devices

Intermediate facilities are affected by 3 types of vertically oriented load:

- * compression from upper horizontal plane cross section;
- * stretching from the lower horizontal plane cross section;
- * compression and cutting on either side of the range in the zone near the supports.

To strengthen the plates and balconies by increasing their cross-section, tension fittings are added to the zones to a large stretch.

With a little reinforcement, additional reinforcement is connected by welding to the existing nearby reinforcement (Figure 2a). To do this, the edge of the lower row of the existing reinforcement is freed from concrete by half the diameter of the sterjens, and New sterjens are welded to them, after which the protective layer is restored by torcreting or by stukaturka.

Increasing the load-bearing capacity of balconies is achieved by increasing their height by 10-20 cm or more. (Figure 2b). In this case, the reinforcement zone is reinforced with a frame consisting of longitudinal and sloping branches and clamps. 3 are welded to the longitudinal reinforcement to the existing 1. Since the bending moments are reduced, reinforcement fittings to the neck can be stretched along the length of the balcony. The ends of the disconnected sterjens are welded

or attached to the existing armature with oblique sterjens. The diameter of the fittings is determined based on the calculation, but at least 12 mm is obtained at the expense of welding. After installing the reinforcement frame, the reinforcement zone is concreted using a mold (Figure 2c). The concrete mixture is compacted with vibrators. In order for old and New concretions to hold reliably, the old surface of the concrete must be thoroughly cleaned of dirt and dust, weak concrete is removed, existing cracks are strengthened, opened amatura is cleaned of rust [3,4].

Figure 2. Additional reinforcement of the reinforced concrete balcony. a-welding an additional armature to an existing armature close by. B-welding the additional armature with an increase in the height of the beam. C-mold for concreting the reinforcement zone. 1-available fittings. 2-new concrete for reinforcement zone. 3-additional fittings. 4-vaccination. 5-tilt additional fittings. 6-vertical homut. 7-oblique khomut. 8-mold for concreting the reinforcement zone.

Most often, reinforced concrete elements can be restored by losing their load-bearing capacity, grinding, closing large cracks. At the same time, when reconstructing bridges, deformation of the load-bearing parts of the plates becomes a big problem: rigels, edge biquirality, ribbed plates. The violation occurs

in the effect of bending under the influence of pressure. In this case, the ribs, rigels can be glued with one-sided weaving carbon fiber in the intermediate direction. If the plates do not have stiffening ribs, the load-bearing Rigel is strengthened and with low distance, tapes are laid over the entire plate. Transverse loads are removed with raw materials [6].

RESEARCH RESULTS

The above-mentioned technologies are traditional and often difficult to implement, because due to the application of these technologies, the structures become heavier and thicker. It is considered more convenient to use modern technology for strengthening bridges with carbon fiber instead of such outdated methods.

Due to the constantly increasing load on the bridge supports, it is necessary to strengthen the bridge structures. The reinforcement of bridges with composites is perceived as a modern solution. It is becoming more common to reinforce the intermediate structures, supports and other load-bearing elements of bridges with modern composite materials such as carbon fiber.

Due to the reinforcement of bridge supports with carbon fiber, it is possible to reduce or completely eliminate the likelihood of air temperature changes, moisture changes, deterioration caused by the displacement of the grunt surface [6].

Performs all types of bridge reinforcement with composite materials, including modern restoration with special reinforcing materials – carbon fiber materials [6-8].

Reinforcement begins with a thorough engineering inspection. Experts assess the condition of the object, study the initial project of the bridge, draw up a skastening map and a strengthening project.

Then, as part of the preparation, the surface is cleaned of contamination, defects inside reinforced concrete structures are eliminated, and cracks are filled. At this stage, additional reinforcement with a composite setka is possible.

Strengthening the bridges is carried out according to the approved scheme. It is advisable to do this with a little air humidity, in dry and warm weather (although carbon fiber involves working at any time of the year). The base for laying ugleplastic should be clean and dry.

Reinforcement materials include a fastener based directly on composite tapes and a mixture of lamellas and epoxy. Epoxy glue can only be applied to the reinforcing material or tapes and reinforced supports as well as spacers (depending on the adhesion of the base material).

After the built-in carbon fiber tapes are hardened, the builders perform high-load tests (it can be static or Dynamic). In order to qualitatively measure the final indicators and achieve a long-term result, it is important to use high-quality materials to strengthen the structures. As a result of tests and measurements, documents are drawn up that record the parameters of the object.

Unlike concrete and steel "shirts", carbon fiber does not increase the weight of structures and the load on the foundation of bridge supports. With this method, there are a number of schemes for strengthening structures from various building materials. There is no need to limit movement on bridges for a long time: no at all or minimal. In addition, you do not need special equipment or earthworks to carry out work [6].

CONCLUSIONS

Advantages of using carbon fiber

The use of carbon fiber has a number of advantages over traditional methods:

* small mass of materials in use. Carbon fiber is very compact, so strengthening bridges with carbon fiber practically does not weigh down the structure.

* Hardly thickens reinforced structures when reinforcing intermediate structures of bridges with carbon fiber.

* Simple installation. Carbon fiber material is installed without the use of complex construction equipment, which can be installed by a small team of specialists. In addition, the installation does not take much time.

* Strength of the material. Despite the fact that carbon fiber is a very thin material, strengthening bridge supports with carbon fiber has been shown to be effective alongside traditional methods of strengthening bridges with steel elements.

* Carbon fiber is absolutely inert and the aggressive environment does not affect it. It is not scary in precipitation, not prone to corrosion [6-8].

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